

CHALLENGES AND RESULTS OF MODERN BUSINESS JOURNALISM IN GEORGIA**Marika Sherazadishvili,***Doctor of Philology, Professor of Gori State University,
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ORCID-0000-0002-2500-6252***Abstract**

Modern business journalism in Georgia, against the backdrop of dynamically changing social, economic and technological processes, is experiencing multifaceted challenges that significantly affect the quality, reliability and public function of the media.

The aim of the paper is to comprehensively analyze the main factors that determine the trends in the development of business journalism in the country and its results, both in the context of the journalistic product and the broader business discourse. The above-mentioned challenges include both the difficulties associated with maintaining professional standards and the problems of implementing an independent editorial policy, which in many cases depends on the commercial interests of business information resources. The lack of professional freedom of journalists and the lack of transparency of the personal and often political interests of media owners creates a basis for distrust, which complicates the critical and realistic perception of information by the audience. In addition, technological progress and the spread of digital platforms, on the one hand, increase the accessibility of information and the degree of audience engagement, but on the other hand, lead to an increase in the demand for sensational (often unfounded) content, which affects the quality of the journalistic product.

Keywords: 1. Journalism; 2. Business; 3. Business journalism; 4. Journalistic product; 5. Business media.

Introduction: Modern business journalism in Georgia plays an important role in economic and business processes, the formation of a transparent business environment and raising public awareness. Nevertheless, given the current economic and political context and the specifics of the media environment, this area faces many challenges.

In the context of the development of democratic institutions, media freedom, technological changes and digital transformation, the role of business journalism is becoming increasingly important, which leads to the strengthening of its functions in terms of both objective reporting of information and critical analysis and the formation of public discourse. However, along with these opportunities, a number of challenges are identified that limit the effective work of the media in the business sphere. In particular, many cases indicate that the media in Georgia (and not only in Georgia) often depend on specific political and business interests, which to some extent limits the editorial freedom and independence of journalists and reduces the professional standards of journalistic activity. In addition, the culture of economic and business analytics is not properly developed in Georgia, which further enhances the growth of the share of superficial, sometimes sensational materials in the information flow. The lack of accuracy, fact-based information, and critical analysis remains a significant problem, which is directly reflected in the level of trust of the audience in business media. It is understandable that the spread of digital media and the intensive use of social networks have expanded the area of information dissemination, but at the same time have complicated the mechanisms for con-

trolling the reliability of information. The modern technological environment creates both new opportunities and new threats, which oblige business journalism to adopt more responsible approaches and acquire new skills. In this context, the following questions become particularly relevant: How independent is business news media in Georgia? What is its impact on public opinion? To what extent does journalistic practice comply with professional and ethical standards? What resources are available to strengthen this area?

Review and discussion: The challenges, results and prospects of modern business journalism in Georgia are seen as a kind of tandem of the relationship between the media and society, where urgent needs and challenges are simultaneously the subject of active discussion and assessment for both sides. In Georgian journalism, in particular, in the business direction, there is an increase in such contradictory factors that both complicate and enable the introduction of new practices and standards that can be aimed at increasing transparency, accountability and quality. First of all, the problems of financial sustainability stand out in the package of challenges: a small market and inadequate indicators of commercial income in media organizations limit business journalism in professional excellence in terms of both content and expression, which is accompanied by an acute lack of transparency of owners and editorial independence. Such business journalism is often subject to the influence of the political and business interests of the owners, which leads to predetermined narratives, a relatively small share of critical and analytical material and, consequently, a small or non-existent audience. The safety and freedom of journalists are being violated in various ways: pressure from media business

owners, political interests, increased attempts at legislative regulation and control, which hinder a stable, fair and unhindered environment. Polarization between various business groups that own media outlets and have political interests along with business interests is a serious challenge for business journalism. At the same time, foreign funding sources and donors are emerging, whose media activities, in addition to business interests, also reflect political interests. Financial problems are particularly difficult for regional and small media organizations - the lack of such means and human resources as are needed to produce quality business analytics, investigative journalism and multimedia content. In addition, global and local technological changes, the growth of digital platforms, social networks, algorithms and artificial intelligence, create both opportunities and challenges. The online space provides powerful means of information dissemination and diversity and promotes broad audience engagement, but the creation of high-quality journalistic content requires changes in existing resources, including technical skills and knowledge of information validity and data verification measures, taking into account ethical norms and professional standards. The lack of awareness on the part of the public, the low level of media education and media literacy further hinders the ability of the public to critically understand the product and demand of business media, to have quality analytics and real-fact-based information. Against the background of these challenges, certain - both negative and positive - consequences are evident. Among the negative consequences, the public's negativity towards media trust is evident, when business journalism becomes: a part of the game of political narratives and interest groups; distortion of facts, distortion of content and an increase in the demand for sensation in some media outlets; increased emphasis of regional media products on various self-proclaimed business information portals, the quality of which is often insufficiently constructed or lacking, which reinforces the lack of disinformation and tracking analytics. In particular, journalists and media activists from organizations focus on the problem that some new legislation adopted by the state increases financial and legal threats to the media, which leads to restrictions on the work of independent companies, a decrease in scale and

resources, and the threat of complete closure. Also, the lack of media revenue models, advertising, sponsorship, and international grants often work together but do not create a stable model for business journalism.

Positive results can be considered the growth of independent online publications that manage to introduce multimedia formats, expand their audience at the local and international levels, which significantly strengthen public discourse and influence in political, economic and social circles. Also, decisions on the professional training of journalists and the internal structure of media organizations (policy, ethical standards, research approaches) give hope that the field will gradually be able to cope with the challenges. The perspectives on how business journalism can develop in Georgia are quite diverse, and possible directions include both institutional and professional changes, as well as social and technological innovations. First of all, it is necessary for media organizations and journalists to develop more robust organizational models for independence: transparency of ownership, mechanisms for protecting ethical and editorial independence, and tightening professional codes. Financial sustainability can also be increased through international assistance, but it is more important to increase local revenues. Advertising alone is not enough; subscription models, audience acquisition and support, paid services for specialized content, conferences, research partnerships, and other innovative financial avenues need to be explored. Part of the technological perspective is the further adoption of digitalization, the improvement of the legal environment, the strengthening of media rights organizations and professional associations, the existence of which will create an additional buffer against pressure and risks, and will contribute to the formation of an environment where quality business journalism will gain broad public support and greater responsibility. Ultimately, the development of business journalism in Georgia is linked to the deepening of democracy, economic transparency, and public self-awareness, and its strength is determined not only by the media, but also by the state, the business sector, civil society, and the audience. We present the indicators of the use and trust of business journalism in Georgia. (Table)

Business Journalism Usage and Trust Indicators in Georgia

#	Indicator	Statistics	Data source	Note
1	Share of enterprises using social media for business communication	29.6%	Geostat (2024), iBusiness.ge	Notes that only a small proportion use social media, which limits the dissemination of business news
2	Share of enterprises not using integrated media	70.7%	Geostat (2024)	Perhaps indicating low digital engagement in business communication
3	Share of population using the Internet to read news/magazines/newspapers	46.6%	Geostat (2024)	About half use online media for new information
4	Size of the print media market in Georgia	\$39.43 million (2025)	Statista	Includes newspapers and magazines — many of which also contain business information
5	Share of readers in the print media market (penetration rate)	17.8%	Statista	This indicator indicates a small proportion of consumers who use print media sources
6	Georgia's position in the Media Freedom Index (RSF 2024)	103rd place	RSF / OC Media	A negative signal in terms of trust — trust in the media is low

Conclusion: The development of modern business journalism in Georgia clearly demonstrates the complex, multidimensional nature of the media environment, where issues of professional standards, free speech, technological innovations, economic interests and public awareness are interconnected. It is clear that Georgian business journalism has many systemic and structural challenges to overcome, which include both internal problems, such as: lack of editorial independence, lack of professional ethics, insufficient educational and qualification resources, and external factors, such as: political pressure, influence of owners' interests, financial difficulties and inconsistency with audience expectations. These challenges directly affect the quality of business media, the level of trust and its public role.

Despite the problems, there has been progress in recent years: the growing role of independent online media, youth initiatives in the field of media development, the integration of technological capabilities into journalistic practice, the emergence of data-based analytics, and attempts to introduce professional standards focused on international experience. These processes have somewhat broadened the discourse around business topics and contributed to raising public awareness

of economic issues. However, it is clear that for long-term, sustainable progress, coordinated support from both the state and private and public sectors is necessary, where the media environment is perceived not as a tool of political control or just a commercial platform, but as an integral part of the democratic process.

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